

HyDelta 4

WP5e – Flare geometries for gas mixtures

D5E.1 –Experimental results of a controlled hydrogen flaring installation

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- End use
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- Conversion (of the distribution network)
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System and Economy

- Business Development
- Production and supply
- Value chains

Gas Quality

- Admixing
- Gas Quality
- Odourisation

Executive summary

For the operation of local, regional, and national hydrogen networks, both in preparation for maintenance work or in case of emergencies, operators are required to purge pipeline sections of hydrogen. For safety and environmental reasons, flaring of hydrogen is preferred over venting, as venting hydrogen to the atmosphere should be minimized as much as possible.

Research conducted within HyDelta 2 shows that the flaring installations currently used for this purpose produce nitrogen oxide emissions [1]. The hypothesis of this study is that controlled flaring installations can be used to reduce the amount of emissions.

In the original project description, it was stated that the hypothesis would be tested using a commercially available controlled flaring installation. However, after an extensive market consultation it became clear that no such system was commercially available at the time of the study. To investigate the hypothesis nonetheless, a custom controlled flare installation was designed, built, and tested. This flare system uses a controlled burner that is normally applied in industrial environments. The results of the experimental tests demonstrate that such a burner can be used in a flaring installation to safely neutralize hydrogen from the network, with approximately a tenfold reduction in nitrogen oxide emissions.

The addition of nitrogen does not necessarily have a negative impact on emissions. Flame stability remains acceptable up to a level of 34 vol% nitrogen in hydrogen. When the nitrogen content becomes higher, the burner safety system is triggered and the gas supply is shut off. Since the resulting mixture (of nitrogen, air, and hydrogen) is then below the flammability limit, the remaining volume can be safely vented—though this does result in hydrogen emissions.

This report is written in a pyramid structure. The first two chapters present the results of the experimental research, distinguishing between the intended use of the flare setup for pure hydrogen combustion and the robustness of the setup for mixtures of hydrogen and nitrogen. The third chapter discusses the test setup, and the final chapter describes the findings of the search for a controlled flare system. The report concludes with a summary of the key conclusions and recommendations for potential follow-up research.

Samenvatting

Voor en tijdens de operatie van lokale, regionale en landelijke waterstofnetwerken zijn installaties nodig om leidingdelen productvrij te kunnen maken in geval van onderhoudswerkzaamheden of calamiteiten. Vanuit veiligheid en milieu heeft het affakkelen van waterstof hierbij de voorkeur, het afblazen van waterstof wordt bij voorkeur tot een minimum beperkt.

Uit onderzoek gedaan in HyDelta 2 blijkt dat de fakkelininstallaties die op dit moment hiervoor gebruikt worden stikstofoxide emissies hebben [1]. De hypothese van dit onderzoek is dat geregelde fakkelininstallaties kunnen worden gebruikt om zo de hoeveelheid emissies te reduceren.

In de oorspronkelijke opdracht omschrijving was beschreven dat de hypothese getest zou worden met een geregelde fakkelininstallatie uit de markt. Na een uitgebreide marktconsultatie bleek dat er ten tijde van het onderzoek geen geregelde fakkelininstallatie commercieel verkrijgbaar was. Om de hypothese toch te onderzoeken is een eigen geregelde fakkelininstallatie ontworpen, gerealiseerd en getest. Deze fakkelininstallatie werkt met een geregelde brander welke normaal gebruikt wordt in industriële omgevingen. De resultaten van de experimentele testen bewijzen dat een dergelijke brander kan worden ingezet als fakkelopstelling om, met ongeveer een factor 10 minder stikstofoxide uitstoot, waterstof uit het net onschadelijk te maken.

Ook bijmenging van stikstof hoeft geen negatieve invloed te hebben op de emissies. De vlamstabiliteit blijft acceptabel tot een niveau van 34 vol% stikstof in waterstof. Wanneer het aandeel stikstof groter wordt zal de vlambeveiliging in werking treden en wordt de gastoevoer gesloten. Aangezien het mengsel (van stikstof, lucht en waterstof) zich dan onder de brandbaarheidsgrens bevindt, kan het resterende deel hierna veilig, maar met waterstof emissies, worden afgeblazen.

Deze rapportage is in piramide stijl geschreven. In de eerste twee hoofdstukken worden de resultaten gegeven van het experimentele onderzoek, waarbij een opsplitsing is gemaakt tussen het beoogde gebruik van de fakkelopstelling voor pure waterstof verbranding en de robuustheid van de fakkelopstelling voor mengsels van waterstof en stikstof. In het derde hoofdstuk zal de testopstelling besproken worden en in het laatste hoofdstuk zullen de resultaten van de zoektocht naar de geregelde fakkelininstallatie worden beschreven. Er zal worden afgesloten met een herhaling van de belangrijkste conclusies en de aanbevelingen voor eventueel vervolgonderzoek.

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2. Emissions can be lowered by optimizing the air-fuel ratio

As a starting point of the research, the initial status of the burner was mapped. From this, it can be concluded that the maximum capacity of the flare arrangement is around 150 m³/hour (13.5 kg/hour; 500 kW) with a burner efficiency of more than 99%. In addition, the NO_x emissions have been determined, which shows that these emissions can be reduced by adjusting the gas-to-air ratio of the combustion process.

The functional performance of the hydrogen burner is described in this chapter. More insight into the design of the flare arrangement and the measurement locations can be found in chapter 4. At the start of the measurements, the first thing determined was the nominal settings, supplied by the supplier, of the burner (section 1.2.1). For different pipe geometries, an estimate is made of the time required to depressurize these pipe sections based on the maximum capacity that the hydrogen burner can handle, this is described in section 2.2. Subsequently, the efficiency of the burner is assessed, i.e. the amount of hydrogen that is actually converted during the combustion process. NO_x emissions from hydrogen combustion are discussed in section 1.2.4, where optimization possibilities are also mentioned. Finally, the impact of the burner on the environment in terms of heat radiation is assessed.

All measurements described in this report were carried out in the open air, which means that measurements were not performed under conditioned environmental conditions. In addition, the measurements were carried out over different days and parts of the day. As a result, there may be a slight variation in measurement results. As far as possible, corrections have been made for prevailing environmental conditions at the location of the measurement location. In conclusion, it can be stated that the measurement results presented in this report are of an indicative nature.

2.1. With the factory air-fuel ratio of the burner, it functions sufficiently

After building the burner flaring setup, the determination of the nominal settings was commenced. The modulation range is defined by determining the minimum and maximum load. It was decided to carry out most measurements at 3 load points. The low-load point (Load sp20), this was the lowest setpoint that was adjustable on the burner, with a power of about 120 kW. The high-load point (Load sp100), this was the highest adjustable setpoint, with a power of about 470 kW. And a point in between (Load sp60) was chosen to have a measuring point in the middle range at about 320 kW.

At these loads, the gas-air setting (λ) is determined on the basis of the oxygen concentration in the flue gases. Figure 1 shows the gas-air settings over the burner's modulation range. From this it can be deduced that the modulation range (capacity) of the burner runs from 120 kW to 470 kW. The lowest gas-air setting, λ of 1.60, is found at the low-load operating point of the burner. At the other end of the modulation range, the λ is around a value of 1.50. In the middle range, the richest combustion setting (λ of 1.30) was measured.

Figure 1: Nominal air-fuel ratio of the burner.

2.2. The maximum achievable flare capacity is 508 kW.

The maximum capacity of the hydrogen flaring plant depends on the control valve settings for both fuel and air, as described in section 4.2 of this report. When fully opening the gas control valve, the maximum capacity of the flare arrangement is determined. The nominal (set maximum by supplier) and maximum achievable (Kiwa tested) settings of the burner are shown in Table 1. From this it can be concluded that the maximum hydrogen flow rate of the burner is 154 [m³/hour]. By further opening the gas control valve, the gas-air mixture becomes richer. The fuel-air ratio (λ) has decreased from 1.46 to 1.38, resulting in a fuel increase of about 8%. The determination of the maximum gas flow rate was carried out at a dynamic gas input pressure of 125 [mbar].

Table 1: Nominal and maximum gas-air settings of the hydrogen flaring installation at a gas pre-pressure of 125 [mbar].

	Nominal	Maximal
Gas control valve position [%]	88	100
Air control valve position [%]	99	99
Lambda [-]	1.46	1.38
Gas flow rate [m ³ /h]	143	154
Power [kW]	472	508

For a number of combinations of pipe lengths and diameters in combination with a prevailing pressure in the pipe, a normal volume of gas has been calculated. The calculation was based on an ideal gas and therefore the ideal gas law was used. This gives an indication of the normal volumes present, which are shown in Table 2. The effect of the compressibility factor has been calculated and is negligible.

Table 2: Normal volume table for different pipe geometries and prevailing pressures. Calculated with the ideal gas law.

Pipeline volume [m3]								
Geometry		Pressure [bar(a)]						
L [m]	D [m]	0,5	1	10	20	30	50	66
50	0,10	0,2	0,4	4	8	12	20	26
50	0,20	1	2	16	31	47	79	100
50	0,35	2	5	48	96	140	240	320
50	0,60	7	14	140	280	420	710	930
200	0,10	1	2	16	31	47	79	100
200	0,20	3	6	63	130	190	310	410
200	0,35	10	19	190	380	580	960	1300
200	0,60	28	57	570	1100	1700	2800	3700
1000	0,10	4	8	79	160	240	390	520
1000	0,20	16	31	310	630	940	1600	2100
1000	0,35	48	96	960	1900	2900	4800	6300
1000	0,60	140	280	2800	5700	8500	14000	19000
2000	0,10	8	16	160	310	470	790	1000
2000	0,20	31	63	630	1300	1900	3100	4100
2000	0,35	96	190	1900	3800	5800	9600	13000
2000	0,60	280	570	5700	11000	17000	28000	37000
10000	0,89	3100	6200	62000	120000	190000	310000	410000
10000	1,20	5700	11000	110000	230000	340000	570000	750000

Based on the normal volumes of gas present in the calculated pipe sections and the maximum flare capacity, see Table 2, an estimate can be made for the required flare time for the pipeline to be released from atmospheric pressure. The flare time is shown for the same flare geometries and pressure combinations in Table 3.

Table 3: Required flaring time for different pipe geometries and prevailing pressures.

Required flaring time [d:hh:mm]								
Geometry		Pressure [bar(a)]						
L [m]	D [m]	0,5	1	10	20	30	50	66
50	0,10	0:00:00	0:00:00	0:00:01	0:00:03	0:00:04	0:00:07	0:00:10
50	0,20	0:00:00	0:00:00	0:00:06	0:00:12	0:00:18	0:00:30	0:00:40
50	0,35	0:00:00	0:00:01	0:00:18	0:00:37	0:00:54	0:01:33	0:02:03
50	0,60	0:00:02	0:00:05	0:00:54	0:01:49	0:02:43	0:04:36	0:06:03
200	0,10	0:00:00	0:00:00	0:00:06	0:00:12	0:00:18	0:00:30	0:00:40
200	0,20	0:00:01	0:00:02	0:00:24	0:00:50	0:01:14	0:02:00	0:02:41
200	0,35	0:00:03	0:00:07	0:01:14	0:02:31	0:03:45	0:06:14	0:08:14
200	0,60	0:00:10	0:00:22	0:03:42	0:07:08	0:11:02	0:18:10	1:00:14
1000	0,10	0:00:01	0:00:03	0:00:30	0:01:02	0:01:33	0:02:31	0:03:21
1000	0,20	0:00:06	0:00:12	0:02:00	0:04:05	0:06:06	0:10:23	0:13:27
1000	0,35	0:00:18	0:00:37	0:06:14	0:12:20	0:18:49	1:07:10	1:17:14
1000	0,60	0:00:54	0:01:49	0:18:10	1:13:00	2:07:11	3:18:54	5:01:10
2000	0,10	0:00:03	0:00:06	0:01:02	0:02:00	0:03:03	0:05:07	0:06:43
2000	0,20	0:00:12	0:00:24	0:04:05	0:08:26	0:12:20	0:20:07	1:02:55
2000	0,35	0:00:37	0:01:14	0:12:20	1:00:40	1:13:39	2:14:20	3:10:28
2000	0,60	0:01:49	0:03:42	1:13:00	2:23:25	4:14:23	7:13:49	10:02:21
10000	0,89	0:20:11	1:16:23	16:19:58	33:14:00	50:30:00	84:03:00	111:00:00
10000	1,20	1:12:43	3:01:26	30:14:23	61:05:00	91:19:00	153:00:00	202:00:00

2.3. The combustion efficiency of the flare installation is >99.9%

The efficiency of the hydrogen flare is expressed in the percentage of hydrogen that is actually burned. By measuring the amount of unburned hydrogen in the flue gases, the efficiency of the flare can be

determined. For the nominal settings as shown in Figure 1, the results are plotted in Figure 2. The maximum hydrogen concentration appears to remain below 140 ppm with the given gas-air setting and thus the efficiency of the flare comes to 99.986%.

Figure 2: Unburned hydrogen concentration in flue gases at the nominal gas-air settings.

The efficiency of the hydrogen flaring installation has also been investigated for changing gas-air settings. After all, it is to be expected that higher concentrations of unburned hydrogen can occur for lean mixtures because the flame can blow off. At each of the three load points in Figure 2, the λ was increased, as high as possible, and the unburned concentration of hydrogen was measured. These graphs are shown in Figure 3. Measurements have shown that up to about $\lambda=3.5$ the combustion remains stable and the amount of unburned hydrogen is very low. From $\lambda=3.5$ onwards, the hydrogen emission increases, with the maximum concentration found being 350 ppm at the full load point for $\lambda>7.0$. This brings the efficiency down to 99.965%.

From the gas-air ratio where flame loss occurs, the burner efficiency will not decrease further. The flame protection, as described in paragraph 4.2, ensures that the burner goes into a closed state as the gas valves are automatically closed. As a result, there is no outflow of hydrogen through the burner without a flame.

Figure 3: Hydrogen concentration in the flue gases as a function of gas-to-air ratio for three different load setpoints (Load setpoints).

In summary, it can be said that the flaring installation can meet an efficiency of more than 99.95% over the entire operating range of the burner. Under optimized gas-air conditions, it is even possible to achieve a flare efficiency of 99.99%.

2.4. NOx emissions reduce when the mixture is leaner

In contrast to the combustion of hydrocarbons, the combustion of hydrogen does not produce CO₂ and CO emissions, but NO_x emissions can still occur. These NO_x emissions depend strongly on the gas-air setting of the burner. The cooling effect of air lowers the flame temperature, resulting in lower NO_x emissions. Figure 4 shows the normalized (compensated for residual air) NO_x emissions plotted against λ for the different load points. From this it can be concluded that the NO_x emissions decreases sharply from the lowest values to about a lambda of 2 to 2.5 and from there it shows a more moderate decrease. Where a slight increase can even be seen for the lowest load point.

Figure 4: NO_x emissions (air free) as a function of gas-to-air ratio for three different load points.

The NO_x emissions from this flare installation can be compared to the measured¹ NO_x emissions found during HyDelta 2 WP5.1 [1]. During HyDelta 2, a standard open pipe flaring installation was tested with hydrogen. This is a unregulated installation and only has a diffusion flame, that is, 100% hydrogen comes out of the burner nozzle after which it mixes with air and then the formed mixture burns. During this measurement, the highest amount of NO_x measured was 848 ppm. This is an indicative value because the influence of the wind on an open pipe burner cannot be measured properly. The actual emissions are thought to be higher rather than lower because only gusts of (diluted) exhaust gas were measured during this study. Independently of this, this comparison shows that significantly lower NO_x emissions can be achieved with a regulated flare installation.

2.5. The heat radiation around the flare installation does not pose a danger

As part of the tests, the released heat radiation was measured and recorded. The heat radiation (also called heat flux) in full-load operation remained below 4 kW/m² in all cases. The heat radiation with a chimney was higher than the radiation without a chimney.

Figure 5 shows a schematic representation of the position of the radiation meter during the tests. The radiation meter was placed at a distance of 1 meter, about halfway up the chimney. This height was chosen because the chimney glowed the most here. It is therefore plausible that most radiation would be measured here. If measurements were taken further away, or at a different height, the heat radiation will be lower. Measurements were also taken without a chimney, the heat radiation sensor remained at the same location. A Hukseflux HF03-LI19 was used which registers an average value over a period of 2 seconds.

Figure 5: Sketch showing the location of the radiation meter in relation to the burner and the chimney.

Figure 6 shows two graphs. Left in the graph the heat radiation with a chimney, right without a chimney. Two things stand out here:

1. With a chimney, there is more heat radiation than without a chimney. This is because the chimney becomes "red hot" during full-load operation. The slow heating and cooling of the chimney can be clearly seen in the rising and falling edge of the line in the graph.

¹ Experiments conducted in which wind has an impact on the results found during the measurements.

- Without a chimney, the heat radiation is more irregular than with chimney. The mass of the chimney dampens rapid temperature changes. In addition, the chimney strongly decreases wind influences. During operation without a chimney, it was found that the wind significantly influenced the direction and shape of the flame. This has a direct effect on the measured radiated heat.

Figure 6: The heat radiation of the flare installation with chimney (left) and without chimney (right).

Both findings were consistent with what was felt during the testing process. More heat was felt at the chimney, while without a chimney the flames were easily approachable before it got hot. For protective firefighting clothing that complies with NEN-EN 469 [2], the limit is 4 kW/m². The measured values are below that. Since radiation decreases with increasing distance from the source, there is no danger to humans. Even at a distance of 1 meter, a mechanic in mechanic's clothing will not experience permanent injury from a short exposure to such heat radiation. If this is too much heat radiation for such an installation, an extra ventilated pipe can be placed over the chimney which would decrease radiation to near zero.

3. Blending in nitrogen affects the emissions of the hydrogen flare

By mixing nitrogen into the hydrogen flow, the flame stability is negatively affected. As a result, the efficiency of the flare also decreases, because the concentration of unburned hydrogen in the chimney increases. A positive effect of the extra nitrogen in the gas pipeline is that NO_x emissions decrease.

When flaring a hydrogen pipe section, flaring will be done until the desired pressure drop in the specific pipe section is achieved. Subsequently, the remaining hydrogen is pressed out of the pipeline using nitrogen. During this process, a hydrogen and nitrogen mixture will be formed, which will arrive at the flaring installation at some point. One of the research questions is to investigate the extent to which the hydrogen burner is able to handle such mixtures. In response to this 1.3.1, the impact of nitrogen dilution on flame stability was assessed in 3.1, whereby it can be concluded that the burner is very tolerant to nitrogen admixing. This is reflected in the fact that flame loss only occurs at full load at a λ of about 6, which calculates to a mixture ratio of 34% nitrogen in the pipeline.

3.1. With a nitrogen-hydrogen mixture up to $\lambda > 4.5$, the flame remains stable

With an increasing concentration of nitrogen in the hydrogen supply, the flame stability decreases. Figure 7 shows the gas-air ratio as a function of the volume concentrations of hydrogen and nitrogen. Due to increasing flame instability from a λ of about 4.5, it is no longer possible to continue burning at a λ value of more than 6.0 in the full load operation of the burner. Around this value, the burner shuts off the gas supply based on the flame protection. This means that the maximum concentration of nitrogen in hydrogen, at which the flare plant remains in operation, is 34 vol%.

Figure 7: Percentages of nitrogen and hydrogen in the gas mixture plotted against the gas-air ratio at full load.

The absolute volume flow rate of the gas mixture decreases continuously during the mixing process, as shown in Figure 7. Due to the density difference of nitrogen compared to hydrogen, the total density of the gas mixture increases. This results in a decrease in the total gas mixture flow rate through the burner head. The absolute volume flows of the hydrogen, nitrogen and the gas mixture are shown as a function of the gas-air ratio in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Volume flow rates of hydrogen, nitrogen and the gas mixture plotted against λ at maximum load.

During the blending process, emissions of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and hydrogen were measured, see Figure 9. This shows that NO_x emissions show a constant downward trend during the nitrogen blending process. The concentration of unburned hydrogen in the flue gases shows an increasing trend from an λ of 3.0 that correlates with the increasing flame instability. This instability is also increasingly audible acoustically from a λ of 4.0 to the point where flame loss occurs. When a flame loss occurs, a gas mixture will flow out that in theory may just be flammable. However, this is so diluted that when it mixes even a bit with the ambient air, it is no longer flammable. If it does become ignited again, it will probably not be visible or noticeable. In theory, the flame could return to the burner bed, but due to the control of the burner, it will not create a dangerous situation. Blowing off the nitrogen/hydrogen through the burner is only possible when the flame protection is bypassed.

Figure 9: NO_x emissions (left axis) and hydrogen emissions (right axis) as a function of gas-air ratio at full load operation of the flare installation.

The impact of nitrogen admixture described above for the full load operating point of the burner has also been investigated for the low-load operating point. In Figure 10 and Figure 11 respectively, the

volume flows and emission measurements are shown for low-load setting of the burner. Similar trends are visible, i.e. a decreasing curve for NO_x emissions and an increase in hydrogen emissions with a higher nitrogen percentage in the gas mixture. Furthermore, a slight shift has been observed in the gas-to-air ratio at which the increase of unburned hydrogen in the chimney begins. Flame instability occurs earlier in low-load operation than when the burner is set to full load.

Figure 10: Percentages of nitrogen and hydrogen in the gas mixture plotted against the gas-air ratio at low-load setting of the installation.

Figure 11: NO_x emissions (left axis) and hydrogen emissions (right axis) as a function of gas-air ratio at low load setting of the flare installation.

3.2. Adding nitrogen results in lower NO_x emissions.

Nitrogen emissions from the experiment in which the gas-air setting of the burner was adjusted, as described in chapter 3, were compared with the nitrogen emissions during the mixing of nitrogen, as described in this chapter. This comparison is shown in Figure 12. NO_x emissions are reduced when

nitrogen is added. By adding nitrogen, the flame temperature is lowered. This results in lower NO_x emissions with the same setting of gas-to-air ratio for the burner.

Figure 12: Comparison of nitrogen emissions between a rising lambda and nitrogen admixture at low load setting of the burner.

4. A controlled flare installation can be made with an forced draft burner

The hydrogen burner used for the research is described in this chapter. The first section describes the gas mixing line, which can supply both pure hydrogen and hydrogen-nitrogen mixtures to the burner. Subsequently, in section 4.2, an overview is given of the arrangement of the burner which was used to carry out the functional measurements on the burner.

Figure 13: Assembly of hydrogen burner to the frame during the construction of the flare installation.

4.1 A hydrogen and nitrogen mixing system has been developed for this research

The purpose of the research is to investigate the suitability of a controlled burner for pure hydrogen flaring as well as for mixtures of nitrogen and hydrogen. To make this possible, a gas mixing line has been designed, which is schematically shown in Figure 14. The gases required for this, hydrogen and nitrogen, are supplied from cylinder packages with pressures of 300 and 200 bar respectively.

Figure 14: Diagram of the gas line assembly used during the measurements.

After the hydrogen package, a first pressure reduction step takes place from the pressure in the bundle to a pressure of 8 bar. Subsequently, an overpressure protection was installed, which serves as extra

safety in the event of an open-failing pressure reducer. The 8 bar pipe section also contains the gas meter, pressure meter and temperature gauge to determine the hydrogen gas flow rate. Subsequently, the pressure is reduced to approximately 120 mbar in two steps. This pressure is the fuel pressure provided to the burner. The components used (except for the first pressure reducer) have been developed for natural gas and do not have a hydrogen certificate. For these components no strange or adverse effects have been noted by using hydrogen instead of natural gas. However, this is only a relatively short test in which the components were only exposed to hydrogen for a few days.

Parallel to the hydrogen supply, a nitrogen supply has been created, which consecutively consists of a pressure reducer, overpressure protection and flow regulator that then flows into the 120 mbar hydrogen pipeline section. The mass flow controller is used both as a regulator and as a flow meter of the nitrogen flow.

Figure 15: Photo of the gas mixing line where hydrogen (8 bar) is supplied from above and nitrogen from the bottom right, and then flows towards the flare installation (downwards).

4.2 A flare installation has been developed and built with an integrated hydrogen burner

Figure 16 shows a 3D CAD image of the setup with the hydrogen burner, as used for the flare survey. The burner is mounted on a frame where the burner head is vertically oriented, in contrast to the more common arrangement where an attachment burner is mounted horizontally in a boiler. In addition, a chimney has been installed to allow the flue gases to flow up into the air. A further explanation and dimensioning of the chimney is described in section 4.3.

Figure 16: 3D CAD design of the flaring test installation.

Burner control

The tested hydrogen flaring installation is regulated in this study. Figure 17 shows a schematic representation of the main components of the gas-air assembly of the hydrogen burner. On the input side of the burner, the inlet pressure (1) is measured (this is the point where the gas mixture is taken over from the supply described in section 4.1). Subsequently, the gas flows through the gas valve, which is formed by two separate pilot valves (3 & 5), surrounded by three pressure sensors (2, 4 & 6) which are used to:

1. Prevent the burner from switching on when the gas pre-pressure is too low;
2. Check for leakage through the gas valve;
3. Switch off if the gas line pressure is too low or too high.

Finally, the gas flows through an electronically actuated butterfly valve, which can be used to regulate the gas flow to the burner.

There are also a number of actuators in the air duct, through which the air required for combustion is supplied to the burner. In the lower half of Figure 17 you can see that an electronically actuated butterfly valve (9) and a fan (10) are part of the air supply circuit. The fan ensures the creation of an airflow of the combustion air, whereby the amount of air supply can be regulated with the electronically actuated butterfly valve.

The combination of control valve settings, for both the gas and the air, determines the amount of gas that is burned as well as the gas-air ratio. By default, a curve is stored in the burner with setpoints for both actuators, so that the burner will set the gas-air ratio according to the pre-stored curves at the desired load.

Figure 17: Schematic representation of the gas-air assembly in the hydrogen burner.

Burner start

Before each start of the burner, a cycle is completed in which the following verification steps are carried out by the burner control system:

1. Gas pre-pressure above lower limit;
2. Gas pre-pressure below upper limit;
3. Leakage check of the pilot valves;
4. Gas control actuator cycle check;
5. Air control actuator cycle check.

All of the above control steps contribute to a safe ignition attempt of the burner when it is turned on.

Flame detection

The burner has a flame detection system (number 11 in Figure 17), which continuously checks whether the flame is still present during operation. The moment the flame protection no longer detects a flame, the burner will go into a locked state and closes the pilot valves of the gas valve, with the aim of leaving the appliance in a safe state.

4.3 A chimney is used to be able to carry out the correct measurements

The burner head ends in a chimney that ensures that external influence on the flame, such as wind, remains limited. An opening has been made in the chimney for a probe that allows flue gas extraction, which can be measured with a flue gas analyzer. On the outside of the chimney, four thermocouples are placed around the circumference of the pipe. Figure 18 shows a sketch of the chimney (DN350 RVS316Ti) with the indicated measuring points.

Figure 18: Sketch showing thermocouple and flue gas extraction locations on the chimney.

Figure 19: Hydrogen flaring arrangement including chimney during full load operation.

5. No commercially available flare installations with combustion control have been found

A survey of available mobile hydrogen flare installations with combustion control, has shown that these are currently not available in the market.

The first step of the research into controlled hydrogen flare installations was to approach suppliers of these installations. To get an indication of the market, an desk research was carried out. This resulted in more than 25 market parties that can supply flares. The complete list of companies that have been found on the basis of internet consultation is shown in Table 5.

After an initial selection based on the mobility of the flare and already known suppliers, ten companies have been contacted for a further request for regulated mobile hydrogen flare installations. A summary of the results of suppliers with whom written and/or telephone communication took place is shown in Table 4.

The table shows that two companies were eventually found for mobile hydrogen flares, both flares do not have combustion control. The other suppliers listed indicated that they did not have a mobile hydrogen flare.

Some of the approached suppliers indicated that they were working on developing hydrogen flares and or that they had a solution for gas mixtures in which a maximum amount of hydrogen may be present in the gas mixture. Furthermore, the request for information showed that at the moment, mainly unregulated flares with limited capacity are available for mobile applications.

Table 4. Overview of a number of flare suppliers who responded to the regular hydrogen flare request.²

Supplier	Mobile hydrogen flare available	Capacity	Control loop included	Conclusion
Prema service (DE)	Yes	30.000 – 40.000 Nm ³ /hr	No	Without combustion control , high capacity
Revivogas (SK)	No	-	-	Not available
Zorg Biogas (DE)	No	-	-	Not available
Environtec (AT)	No	-	-	Not available
GT-Himmel (AT)	No	-	-	Flare only capable of burning gas mixtures up to a maximum amount 60 vol% of hydrogen
C-deg (DE)	Yes	150 Nm ³ /hr	Flame detection and temperature control	No combustion control

² De uitvraag heeft plaatsgevonden in de periode van juli t/m augustus 2025.

Table 5: Overview of all flare suppliers found

Oge (DE)	Krohse (CH)	Esders (NL)	Oranjeberg (NL)
Prema Service (DE)	Zeeco (US)	Samia (IT)	CRA (IN)
AFS Group (UK)	Revivogas (SK)	Progeco (IT)	John Zink (US)
Zorg Biogas (DE)	DWS (BE)	Hofstetter (CH)	HydroThane (NL)
Environtec (AT)	Ennox (AT)	Encon Clean Energy (NL)	Uniflare (UK)
GTS (NL)	Enwell (NL)	RMT Anlagenbau (DE)	Lambda (DE)
C-deg (DE)	Himmel Gastechnik (AT)		

6. Conclusion and recommendations

In order to decrease hydrogen and nitrous oxide emissions during flaring, a hydrogen flare with controlled combustion can be utilized. However, in this work package it was found that mobile controlled hydrogen flare installations are currently not available in the market. As a result, a flaring installation was developed and made for this research based on a forced draft burner. This installation burns hydrogen with an efficiency of more than 99%. By using a controlled flaring installation, the NO_x emissions can be reduced by about a factor of 10 compared to an open pipe flare installation.

The flaring installation has a maximum capacity of 500 kW, which translates into a hydrogen flow rate of more than 150 m³/hour. Hydrogen forced draft burners with larger capacities are also available, the manufacturer of the burner supplies this type of burner up to 60 MW. This makes it possible to apply the same principle for larger capacities, even when it is made mobile mounted on a skid or trailer.

By increasing the amount of air in the gas-air mixture, NO_x emissions decrease, but this cannot be increased indefinitely. Due to increasing flame instability, a mixture in which the λ is greater than 4.5 results in an increase in hydrogen emissions and thus a decreasing flare efficiency.

The performance of the flaring installation has also been investigated when admixing nitrogen in the hydrogen supply. By adding nitrogen, the limit of flame instability shifts to lower λ values. As a result, the hydrogen emissions in the flue gases are more likely to increase, resulting in a decreasing efficiency of the flare setup. However, this will never lead to flammable concentrations at the chimney. On the other hand, the addition of nitrogen has a positive effect on NO_x emissions. By adding more nitrogen to the hydrogen, NO_x emissions decrease.

Recommendations

Keep a close eye on legislation on hydrogen emissions. At the moment, there is no legislation that determines how many emissions may be produced when making pipelines product-free. It is expected that legislation will be made in the future. By being informed of this in time, disinvestments can be prevented.

At the moment, there is no controlled mobile hydrogen flare installation available on the market. This is probably due to the currently limited demand for controlled mobile hydrogen flare installations. It is important that the market is monitored by the grid operators, for example by regularly organizing a tender. If necessary, the market can even be (financially) stimulated to take up this development.

The step in emission reduction by going from uncontrolled to controlled combustion is relatively big, any differences between manufacturers or burner types are believed to be relatively small. If even less emission is required, flameless alternatives can be used, such as a setup based on catalytic hydrogen conversion. Because the temperature with this method remains below the thermal NO_x limit, the NO_x emissions are virtually zero.

It is also possible to further reduce emissions by making adjustments to the flare geometries as used in this study. This can include:

1. Research the geometry of the burner head. Location and distribution of gas injectors in the burner head affect the flame distribution and stability. In addition, the distribution and flow

of the air also have an influence. By making adjustments to this, the hydrogen burner can be optimized for use in a flare installation.

2. Another well-known way to reduce NO_x emissions is the use of flue gas recirculation. In a future study, it can be investigated whether this can be integrated into the current setup.

The current frame of the flare installation has been designed as a test set-up. To use the setup as a mobile hydrogen flare setup, improvement is desirable to simplify transportability. This can be done, for example, by mounting the installation on a trailer or skid where the connection hose, earth cable and generator are already mounted.

Additional safety measures also have to be considered, the setup used is an experimental setup that must be accessible for measurement equipment. In an operational hydrogen flare installation, there must be no surfaces that can become hot to touch. The chimney would have to be passively cooled and there would have to be a touch-safe shield around it. In addition, the installation must be solid enough to handle the vibrations of transport. The safety devices related to hydrogen combustion are integrated into the burner, so that the burner can only function when everything is working properly. However, pressure reduction and overpressure protection must be added to the installation to be able to deal with the hydrogen transport pipeline pressure.

In addition, the ease of operation should be improved by improving both the "Human Interface Device" and the mechanical connections. This could include a number of buttons that can be pressed to start the burner instead of a touch display in which many different options and settings can be adjusted. The mechanical couplings and connectors must correspond to the connections and procedures used by the network operator. With these further developments, a hydrogen flare installation based on a controlled burner can be easily and quickly integrated into the existing procedures and working methods.

References

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Appendix I: Comparing flaring experiments and CFD results

Introduction

In WP5e of the HyDelta 4 project, two activities were carried out on the topic of flaring H₂ gas mixtures. The objective of these work packages is to investigate whether flame-regulated flares can be used to reduce emissions during hydrogen flaring. The focus is on reducing emissions of NO_x and unburnt hydrogen using a regulated flare operating at different fuel flow rates, fuel hydrogen contents, and levels of additional air in the combustion mixture.

The experiments were carried out by KIWA and are described in report D5E.1, while the CFD simulations were performed by TNO and are detailed in Report D5E.2.

In both tasks, the ratios and amounts of H₂, air, and N₂ were varied. Although similar cases were tested and simulated, a one-to-one comparison was unfortunately not possible. In addition, the experiments were performed outdoors under varying weather conditions, which could not be included in the CFD simulations. Therefore, only overall trends can be compared.

In this document, the results of the two tasks are compared and analyzed, with particular emphasis on trends in H₂ and NO_x emissions and temperatures.

Decreasing NO_x with increasing air (O₂) excess

The first trend visible in both approaches is that, as the mixture becomes leaner (i.e., with excess oxygen), NO_x emissions decrease. This can be explained by the lower flame temperature, caused by a lower amount of H₂ relative to the total flow rate. Most of the NO_x generated is so-called thermal NO_x, which forms when the (local) temperature exceeds approximately 1750 K. Figure A1 shows this trend for the CFD results (left) and the experiments (right).

Figure A1: Trends in NO_x emissions as a function of λ / excess O₂. Left: CFD (blue line). Right: experiments at different loads.

Increasing H₂ emissions at high λ

The next trend is that, as the mixture becomes very lean, H₂ emissions increase. This can be attributed to combustion becoming unstable when little fuel is present. Due to turbulence, parts of the mixture can fall below the flammability limit and therefore not combust. This effect is more evident in the experiments than in the CFD simulations because the simulations assume an idealized environment and do not include changing outdoor weather conditions.

This is illustrated in Figure A2, where an increase in H₂ is observed at high λ or at low fuel H₂ content.

Figure A2 H₂ emissions as a function of λ / fuel composition. Left: CFD results.

Temperature

When comparing the measured and computed chimney wall temperatures, the measured temperatures are higher than those computed. At higher load, the experimental temperatures remain approximately the same as for the 330 kW load (Table A1), whereas the CFD results show an increase in temperature (Figure A3). A difference that was found between the simulations and the experiments is the direction of the flame jets. In the experiments the flames are directed outward to the chimney wall, whereas in the simulation the flames are directed upwards to the exit/top of the chimney. Furthermore, for hydrogen flames there is a difference in the radiative heat transfer coefficient (the main source of heat towards the chimney in the simulation) which is considerably lower than the convective heat transfer coefficient (the main source of heat towards the chimney in the experiments). Both these effects might explain the higher experimental temperatures, as well as the relative low temperature increase due to higher loads.

Table A1 Measured temperatures on outside of the chimney at different loads

Avg Heat input [kW]	T ₁ [°C]	T ₂ [°C]	T ₃ [°C]	T ₄ [°C]
120	648	644	628	610
331	760	755	725	723
490	761	772	710	745

Figure A3 Contour plots of outside wall temperature for (left) 10 kg/h (330 kW) and (right) 20 kg/h (660 kW) loads.

Discussion

Overall, the results show that increasing λ (i.e., operating leaner) reduces NO_x emissions, which is desirable. However, if the mixture becomes too lean (high λ), not all hydrogen is burned, which is undesirable. Therefore, the use of a controlled (flame-regulated) flare is recommended, for which an optimum operating point can be identified that minimizes both NO_x and unburnt H_2 emissions. The optimum setting will depend on the specific burner/flare design and its operating conditions.